

ORGANIZING AND CONDUCTING MASS SPORTS EVENTS AMONG STUDENTS

Anorqulov Baxtiyor Norqul o'g'li

baxtiyoranorqulov94@gmail.com

Lecturer of the Department of Methodology of Teaching Sports,

Gulistan State University

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18844366>

Abstract

This article expands the content requirements for developing students' competence in organizing and conducting mass sports events based on innovative and systematic approaches, and proposes a model grounded in the development of system classification. It formulates scientific conclusions and recommendations for enhancing students' competence in organizing and conducting mass sports activities. The current state of this competence is analyzed, and the system, content, conditions, factors, and tools for its further development are examined and expanded.

Keywords: sport, event, mass, competence, students, condition, development, expansion, recommendations, games, modeling, system.

Абстрактный

Разработка модели на основе расширения содержания требований к развитию компетентности организации и проведения массовых спортивных мероприятий у студентов, инновационно-системных подходов и разработки системной классификации. организация и проведение массовых спортивных мероприятий у студентов и разработка рекомендаций. Изучить современное состояние формирования компетенции организации и проведения массовых спортивных мероприятий у студентов, а также расширить систему, содержание, условия, факторы и инструменты.

Ключевые слова: Спорт, событие, публика, компетентность, студенты, статус, развитие, расширение, рекомендации, игры, моделирование, система.

Introduction

Today, increasing attention is being paid to organizing mass sports events among students. The resolutions of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan serve as clear evidence of this focus. In particular, the Resolution "On Measures for the Further Development of Physical Education and Mass Sports," as well as initiatives aimed at developing mass sports in local communities, confirm the growing importance of this sphere.

In the context of globalization, sport is recognized worldwide as one of the leading factors contributing to national development and enhancing a country's international prestige. Physical culture plays an essential role in maintaining public health and ensuring productivity in labor and industry. Ongoing cultural transformations, industrialization, and urbanization processes around the world are among the key factors promoting the growth of sport. Therefore, many developed countries are currently elaborating and implementing strategies to popularize physical education and sport.

In particular, the International Olympic Committee and the FIFA are consistently carrying out systematic measures to promote sports development in both developed and developing countries. These efforts include enhancing the role of physical education in protecting public health, developing competencies in organizing and officiating sports competitions, standardizing sports game methodologies, and establishing systematic sports competitions.

Research is being conducted at scientific research centers and universities in countries such as the United States, United Kingdom, France, Germany, Italy, Spain, Brazil, and Japan on the role of physical education in human health, the widespread use of sports in promoting a healthy lifestyle among the population, the organization and standardization of sports competitions, the expansion of participation in international sporting events, the training of specialists in physical education and sport, and the development of competencies in organizing and officiating competitions in various sports.

In the New Uzbekistan Development Strategy 2022–2026 of the Uzbekistan, specific priorities are defined for the development and support of physical education and sports. In particular:

Goal 67 – Increasing the number of citizens who regularly engage in physical education and sports, raising this indicator to 33 percent by 2026.

Goal 68 – Developing the Olympic and Paralympic movement, including the advancement of team sports included in the Olympic Games (football, handball, basketball, volleyball, rugby, field hockey, water sports) and other sports disciplines.

To achieve these objectives, several key legal acts have been adopted, including:

Resolution No. PQ-201 (April 11, 2022) “On Measures to Bring Youth Involvement in Mass Sports in Local Communities to a New Stage”; Presidential Decree No. PF-6099 (October 30, 2020) “On Measures to Widely Introduce a Healthy Lifestyle and Further Develop Mass Sports”; Presidential Decree No. PF-5924 (January 24, 2020) “On Measures to Further Improve and Popularize Physical Education and Sports in the Republic of Uzbekistan”; Resolution No. 118 of the Cabinet of Ministers (February 13, 2019) “On Approval of the Concept for the Development of Physical Education and Mass Sports in the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2019–2023”; Presidential Decree No. PF-5368 (March 5, 2018) “On Measures to Radically Improve the System of Public Administration in the Field of Physical Education and Sports”; Resolution No. PQ-3031 (June 3, 2017) “On Measures for the Further Development of Physical Education and Mass Sports”; Amendments to the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On Physical Education and Sports” (September 4, 2015).

The present dissertation research contributes, to a certain extent, to the implementation of the tasks defined in these regulatory and legal documents and other normative acts related to this sphere.

At present, many scholars and faculty members of higher education institutions in the Republic are contributing to the study of training physical education teachers. As a result of examining and scientifically analyzing this issue, we have reviewed numerous methodological works, academic literature, treatises, and candidate and doctoral dissertations. During this process, it became evident that the problem has been studied from pedagogical, psychological, social, and economic perspectives, and necessary conclusions have been drawn, with significant work carried out in this field. Researchers who have contributed to these studies include K.D. Yarashov, D.B. Yadgarov, N.A. Khudayberdiyeva, A.A. Meliziyayev, B.O. Turg'unov, O.O. Oripov, Sh.E. Boltayev, M.E. Choriyeva, V.V. Mahmudov, Sh.X. Kojbakhteyev, T.R. Zakirov, L.Y. Petrova, S.V. Kuzminikh, N.G. Sokolov, I.Y. Artemov, S.S. Jilin, N.A. Borovkov, H.Z. Gapparov, H.R. Akhmedov, O.Y. Brovashova, A.N. Korban, I.G. Klepikov, Y.S. Barazgova, L.S. Aristov, A.S. Larin, P.A. Ganin, Y.N. Allyanov, Z.X. Nizametdinova, Y. Polishkene, I.S. Khrikov, A.A. Bolozin, P.V. Vavilov, M.A. Tanina, I.A. Yurasov, V.V. Bondarenko, S.A. Barbashova, Y.Y. Shevtsova, A.O.

Yegorichev, I.M. Butin, A.A. Popova, M.I. Sentizova, A.B. Guryeva, A.S. Starostina, J.X. Adambayev, N.M. Osmonbekova, I.Y. Krosnorutskiy, N.V. Antonov, A.K. Vladiko, R.O. Shakirov, Y.A. Shakirova, V.V. Ponomarev, D.T. Mamirova, V.I. Stolyarov, and other pedagogical researchers from Uzbekistan and abroad.

The focus of the study is the process of developing students' competence in organizing and conducting mass sports events. The subject of the research encompasses the forms, methods, and tools for developing students' competence in organizing and conducting mass sports events. The aim of the study is to develop conclusions and recommendations for enhancing students' competence in organizing and conducting mass sports events.

The specific objectives include:

Studying the current state of students' competence in organizing and conducting mass sports events, and expanding its system, content, conditions, factors, and tools.

Clarifying leading principles, methods, and criteria by broadening the content of students' competence in organizing and conducting mass sports events.

Expanding the requirements for developing students' competence based on innovative and systematic approaches, and designing a model grounded in system classification.

Formulating scientific conclusions and recommendations for developing students' competence in organizing and conducting mass sports events.

Achieving these objectives through studying the current state, expanding the system and content, clarifying principles, methods, and criteria, and developing a model, as well as providing scientific conclusions and recommendations, ensures the effectiveness of the study.

The methodological basis of the research is supported by the works of national and international researchers in pedagogical education, as well as practical specialists. The analyses, experimental studies, and the effectiveness of applied methods have been evaluated using various techniques. Conclusions, suggestions, and recommendations have been implemented in practice and approved by competent authorities.

The scientific significance of the study lies in revealing the essence of the problem, clarifying criteria and indicators for system improvement, explaining the role and content of competence development through professional and operational technologies, and enhancing the system for organizing mass sports events in higher education institutions.

The practical significance of the research is demonstrated by the empirical grounding of the mass sports event organization system, the development of a model for system improvement, highlighting opportunities to develop professional competence in physical education and pedagogy, and improving the process of organizing mass sports events.

Adabiyotlar, References, Литературы:

1. Resolution PQ-3031 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, June 3, 2017, "On Measures for the Further Development of Physical Education and Mass Sports."
2. Presidential Decree PF-5924, January 24, 2020, "On Measures to Further Improve and Popularize Physical Education and Sports in the Republic of Uzbekistan."
3. Resolution PQ-201 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, April 11, 2022, "On Measures to Bring Youth Involvement in Mass Sports in Local Communities to a New Stage."
4. Abdullayev F.T., *Systematic Organization of Mass Physical Education and Health Activities* [Textbook], Tashkent: Umid Design, 2021, 124 pp.

5. Abdullayev F.T., Amanov A.N., Djurayev U., *Organization of Mass Sports and Health Events* [Methodical Guide], Tashkent, 2022, 110 pp.
6. Anorqulov B.N. (2024), "Improving Physical Performance of 9–10-Year-Old Students through Active Games," pp. 393–397.